

Spectrophotometric, Conductometric, and pH Study of the Fe(III) Complex of Quinizarin-2-sulphonic Acid

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Ferric ion with quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid forms a blackish violet, water-soluble complex in 1:1 ratio. Mean K_{eq}° values by continued variation and the mole-ratio methods are respectively 1.85×10^{-4} and 2.307×10^{-4} at 29° and at ionic strength 0.1 (NaCl). Log K values are 3.7324 and 3.6370 and ΔF° are -5.160 and -5.028 kcal./mole. Molecular extinction coefficient comes to 0.02×10^3 at 580 m μ and 7.26×10^3 at 570 m μ .

The reagent 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone-2-sulphonic acid (quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid, abbreviated as QSA) has been investigated in the colorimetric determination of beryllium¹ and aluminium². The mole ratio of the aluminium complex has been established as 1:1. Aqueous, reddish yellow solution of QSA has been found to react with Fe³⁺ ions to form a blackish violet complex which is quite stable and does not precipitate even after 24 hours. QSA solution of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, or further diluted, obeys Beer's law at 570 m μ and 580 m μ at which the complex formation has been studied. The absorbance of FeCl₃ solution of $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, or further diluted, is negligible at these wave lengths. The 1:1 ratio of the complex has been established spectrophotometrically, using Job's method³ of continued variations, mole-ratio method⁴, and slope-ratio method⁵. Conductance and pH studies, using the monovariation method⁶, also confirm the same ratio.

EXPERIMENTAL

Highly pure ferric chloride was used. The iron content was estimated by the oxide method before preparing standard solutions. NaCl and QSA were of B. D. H. AnalaR and chemically pure quality, respectively.

Absorbance measurements were made by means of a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. For conductance measurements, the experimental set up was the same as described previously⁷. The temperature was maintained at $29^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. The pH measurements were carried out by Phillips pH-meter, type GM 4494/96, using the glass electrode,

1. Cucci *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 1358.
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5. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
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7. Joshi and Jain, *this Journal*, 1963, **40**, 241, 242.

type GM 4241. The pH-meter was standardised each time before use with a buffer solution of pH 5. All measurements were carried out after keeping the mixed solutions overnight.

FIG. 1. Absorption spectra studies of mixtures of FeCl_3 and QSA.

Curve A: Reagent = $2.50 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 Curve B: $c = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 0.5$.
 Curve C: $c = 2.50 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 1$.
 Curve D: $c = 1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 2$.
 Curve E: $c = 0.83 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 3$.
 Curve F: $c = 0.62 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 4$.

Nature of the Complex Formed.—

Application of the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁸ (Fig. 1) to the system FeCl_3 -QSA, keeping the total volume 10ml, demonstrates the formation of only one complex, because the region of maximum absorbance of the reagent lies at $450 m\mu$ (curve A), whereas those of the mixtures in 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 ratio of Fe to QSA lie at $470 m\mu$. Since the absorbance of QSA is less than that of the mixture only after $540 m\mu$, $570 m\mu$ and $580 m\mu$ were selected for our study.

Stoichiometry of the Components.—

The composition was established by the afore-mentioned methods³⁻⁶. Observations in large number were taken. Some of the typical results are plotted in Figs. 2 to 7 and summarised in Table I. (Separate figures for observations at $570 m\mu$ and $580 m\mu$ are given to avoid overlapping). In the table c represents the concentration of ferric chloride solution and p , the ratio c'/c (c' being the concentration of QSA solution).

From the table, the ratio of Fe to QSA in the complex comes out to 1:1 and it may be represented as $\text{Fe}(\text{QSA})$.

DISCUSSION

Evaluation of Dissociation Constant, Stability Constant, Free Energy of Formation, and Molecular Extinction Coefficient

(a). *By Job's Method Employing Non-equimolecular Solutions.*—From Fig. 6 it is evident that the peak shifts from the point of stoichiometry of the components in each curve. Hence, using Job's equation³, which holds good only for a 1:1 complex, the mean value of the dissociation constant K_{α} at 29° from curves A and B comes out to 1.852×10^{-4} and stability constant $K = 1/K_{\alpha} = 5.40 \times 10^3$.

TABLE I

Fig. No.	Curve No.	$c \times 10^{-4} M$.	Ionic conc. (μ)	p .	Fixed vol. of one component (ml).	Vol. at the peak (ml).	Total vol. (ml).	Composition of the complex Fe(III): QSA.
A. By Job's method (equimol. soln.).								
2	A	10,000	..	1	..	5.0 FeCl ₃	10.0	1 : 1
	B	6,666	..	1	..	5.0 "	10.0	1 : 1
	C	5,000	..	1	..	5.0 "	19.0	1 : 1
B. By Job's method (non-equimol. soln.).								
6	A	12,500	0.1(NaCl)	0.666	..	5.5 QSA (4.5 FeCl ₃)	10.0	Utilised for finding dissociation constant
	B	10,000	0.1(NaCl)	0.666	..	5.8 QSA (4.4 FeCl ₃)	10.0	
C. By monovariation method (direct and reverse titrations).								
3	A & A ₁	5,000	..	1	20.0	20.0	50.0	1 : 1
4	B & B ₁	4,000	..	1	20.0	20.0	50.0	1 : 1
D. By mole-ratio method.								
5	A	8,333	0.1(NaCl)	1	2.0	2.0 FeCl ₃	12.0	1 : 1
	B	6,666	0.1(NaCl)	1	2.0	2.0 "	12.0	1 : 1
E. By slope-ratio method.								
7	A	9,000	0.1(NaCl)	1	6.0	Parallel Lines	10.0	1 : 1
	B	6,666	0.1(NaCl)	1	6.0		10.0	1 : 1

 FIG. 2. Determination of the composition from absorption spectra studies of equimolecular solutions at 570 m μ and 580 m μ ($p=1$).

 Curve A: $c=1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$.

 Curve B: $c=6.66 \times 10^{-4} M$.

 Curve C: $c=5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$.

FIG. 3. Conductometric and pH direct titration.

Concentrations same as in Fig. 4.

(b). *By Mole-ratio Method.*—From Fig. 5, at 570 m μ and 580 m μ respectively, the value of E_m is 0.142 and 0.140 for curve A and 0.117 and 0.115 for curve B. The corresponding values of E_a are 0.080 and 0.078 for curve A and 0.071 and 0.069 for curve B. Using Harvey and Manning's formulas⁵ for finding α and then K_α , the average value of K_α at 29° comes to 2.307×10^{-4} and that of the stability constant $K = 1/K_\alpha = 4.335 \times 10^3$.

FIG. 4. Conductometric and pH reverse titration.
Curves A & A₁: $c = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 1$.
Curves B & B₁: $c = 4.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 1$.
Curve B₂: $c = 4.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 0$.

FIG. 5. Composition from absorbance studies by the mole-ratio method at 570 m μ and 580 m μ . $p = 1$; $\mu = 0.1$ (NaCl)
Curve A: $c = 8.33 \times 10^{-4} M$.
Curve B: $c = 6.66 \times 10^{-4} M$.

(c). *Free Energy of Formation.*—Using the expression

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K$$

where the terms have their usual significance, the mean values of $\log K$ are 3.7324 and 3.6370 and of ΔF° are -5.160 and -5.028 kcal./mole by Job's continued variation method and mole-ratio method, respectively.

(d). *Molecular Extinction Coefficient by Slope-ratio Method.*—Molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , is equal to the slope of the straight line in which FeCl_3 is varying. From Fig. 7 its mean value comes to 6.02×10^3 at 580 m μ and 7.26×10^3 at 570 m μ .

(e). *Structure of the Complex.*—In Fig. 4, curve B₁ shows that pH of the QSA solution goes on decreasing with the addition of FeCl_3 solution. Curve B₂ shows pH changes of only FeCl_3 solution at similar concentrations. Curve B, lies below B₂, showing that there is an increase in hydrogen-ion concentration in the solution, which is only possible by the liberation of hydrogen ions during complex formation. As one equivalent of QSA is utilised for one equivalent of the Fe^{3+} ion for formation of the complex, the argument advanced by Owens and Yoc⁶ in the structure of Be—naphthazarin 1:1 complex and Be—phenoxyquinizarin sulphonate 1:1 complex may be applied in this Fe—quinizarin sulphonate complex also and its structure may be represented as (1).

FIG. 6. Determination of the dissociation constant from absorption spectra studies of non-equimolecular solutions at 570m μ and 580 m μ . $\mu=0.1$ (NaCl); $p=0.66$.

Curve A: $c=12.5 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 Curve B: $c=10.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

FIG. 7. Composition by the slope-ratio method at 570 m μ and 580 m μ .

$\mu=0.1$ (NaCl); $p=1$; 6 ml excess component + z ml. varying component + $(4-z)$ ml 0.1M-NaCl.
 Curve A: $c=9.00 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 Curve B: $c=6.66 \times 10^{-4} M$.

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